

Probing the Impact of Tribolayers on Enhanced Wear Resistance Behavior of Carbon Rich Molybdenum Based Coatings

Dinesh Kumar D^{a,b,*}, Subhenjit Hazra^a, Kalpataru Panda^c, P. Kuppusami^{a,b}, Tanja Stimpel-Lindner^c, Georg S Duesberg^c

^a Centre for Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai – 60119, Tamil Nadu, India.

^b Centre of Excellence for Energy Research, Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai – 60119, Tamil Nadu, India.

^c Institute of Physics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology, Universität der Bundeswehr, München 85577 Neubiberg, Germany.

*Corresponding Author:

E- mail: ddinesh.tribology@gmail.com (Dinesh Kumar D).

Phone: +91-9976563823

Abstract

Minimizing friction and wear is one of the continuing challenges in many mechanical industries. Recent research efforts have been focused on accelerating the anti-friction and anti-wear properties of hard coatings through the incorporation of self-lubricant materials or the development of new architectures. In this present study, carbon-rich MoC, MoCN, and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings were deposited using reactive magnetron sputtering. XRD, XPS, and Raman spectroscopy were used to evaluate their properties, which revealed the presence of ceramic cubic crystallites, covalent bonds between primary elements, and an excess of amorphous carbon (a-C) in all of the coatings. The multilayer architecture and possible segregation of a-C around the ceramic crystallites resulted in improved mechanical properties for all coatings, with MoC/MoCN coatings having a maximum hardness of 21 GPa and elastic modulus of 236 GPa. Friction and wear behavior are initially determined by the structural–composition–property relationships of the respective coatings; later, the tribological characteristics are altered depending on the nature of tribolayer on both mating surfaces at the contact interface. The highest wear resistance of multilayer MoC/MoCN

coating ($8.7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$) and MoC coating ($3.9 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$) was due to the dissipation of contact stress by the tribofilm consisting of carbon tribo products like graphitic sp^2 carbons, diamond-like sp^3 carbons, and pyrrolic-N. On the other hand, MoCN coating depicted lower wear resistance due to the frequent termination of C-H bonds by N, which restricts the strong formation of tribofilms as well as poor mechanical properties.

Keywords: Carbon-rich coating; multilayer coating; mechanical properties; tribo-film; sp^2 and sp^3 carbons; wear resistance.

1.0 Introduction

Friction and wear loss are the primary challenges for many mechanical industries as these factors not only affect the global energy and economy but also the emission of greenhouse gases like CO_2 .^{1,2} Hard coatings with high wear resistance, and low friction properties were widely studied and utilized as protective coatings on mechanical components in the last few decades. So far, several metal nitrides, carbides, carbonitrides, and chalcogenide coatings have been extensively studied in this regard.^{3,4} However, many cutting-edge tribological components are still demanding advanced wear resistance coatings towards smoother and prolonged performances. Recently, molybdenum-based coatings have shown promising characteristics for advanced tribological applications. For example, MoS and Mo-S-N coatings exhibit low friction (<0.1) and superior wear resistance ($8.6 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$) performance in vacuum conditions due to their basally oriented structure; however, they are highly sensitive to oxygen contamination in ambient conditions, resulting in high friction and wear.⁴⁻⁶ On the other hand, MoN coatings exhibit improved mechanical properties ranging from 13–30 GPa depending on the deposition method and conditions; and shows low friction of ~ 0.3 as well as improved wear resistance of $1.36 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$.^{7,8} The incorporation of carbon in to the MoN system improves the hardness to 28 GPa and significantly reduces the wear rate to $0.59 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$.⁸⁻¹⁰ Warcholinski et al. (2017) achieved a maximum

hardness of 44 GPa for MoN and 38 GPa for MoCN coatings deposited using the cathodic arc method, with MoCN having the lowest wear rate of $4.7 \pm 1.6 \times 10^{-17} \text{ m}^3/\text{Nm}$.¹¹ Although MoN and MoCN coatings show improved tribological characteristics along with good adhesion to the metallic substrates; excessive formation of surface oxides leads to higher wear.^{8,12,13} In this regard, nanocomposite coatings of MoN and MoCN with soft metals which have low shear strength (Cr, Ag, Au, etc.) have been generally utilized to improve wear resistance and high-temperature stability.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Although, the high-temperature tribological properties of soft metals doped MoN and MoCN coatings have been extensively reported in the literature, the room temperature tribological performance of Mo based carbide and carbonitride coatings are rather contradictive demonstrating either high or low friction and wear.

Carbon rich metal carbide coatings (such as TiC:a-C, WC:a-C, and ZrC:a-C, etc) are becoming recent research interest worldwide as the coatings deliver superior tribological performances.^{15,17,18} The sp^2/sp^3 nature of the excess carbons situated around the ceramic crystallites provide low friction and wear characteristics of these coatings. In this crystalline – amorphous combined structure, the formation of easy shearing of C–H bonds in ambient atmosphere due to higher dissipation of contact stress followed by lower friction coefficient.^{17,18} Nevertheless, the properties of carbon rich MoC (MoC:a-C) coatings for tribological applications have not been fully explored which will be worth studying. Moreover, the addition of nitrogen as a third component in the carbon rich MoC:a-C could be evidenced by interesting tribological characteristics because of the combined a-C and carbonitride structures.⁹ Our previous study on MoC coatings demonstrated the promising friction and wear resistance characteristics under ambient and vacuum tribological conditions.¹⁹ It is worth studying the unexplored tribological properties of Mo based carbide and carbonitride coatings to extend our previous findings on MoC coatings. Furthermore, the multilayer concept has recently gained much attention due to its superior tribological

performance as a result of the strengthening mechanisms at alternate layer interfaces; however, require careful optimization of hardness, and modulus to achieve superior tribological properties.²⁰

In addition, tribochemical reactions play a crucial role in governing the friction and wear characteristics of interacting surfaces. Since the oxidation, transfer layers, chemical reactions, phase change, etc., have been directly influencing the mechanical and tribological properties of the coatings during the prolonged interactions and performances.^{21,22} Aim of this present study is to develop the carbon rich MoC (MoC:a-C) coatings with the addition of N adatoms and the multilayer architecture of MoC/MoC(N) to explore their detailed structural, mechanical, and tribological properties. This study also examines the comprehensive tribochemistry, and tribolayer analysis of carbon rich MoC, MoCN, and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings in detail. This study explores the new multilayer architecture for the highly demanding wear resistance applications in various industries.

2.0 Experimental Details

2.1 Deposition of Coatings

The MoC, MoCN, and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings were deposited on polished 316 L stainless steel (SS) and Si (100) substrates using DC magnetron sputtering (Plassys MP300, France). High purity molybdenum (Mo) target with 50 mm diameter and 3 mm thickness was used as source material. The chamber was evacuated up to the base pressure of 3×10^{-4} Pa using rotary and turbomolecular pumps. The working pressure was maintained at 0.2 Pa with the mixture of argon (Ar), methane (CH₄), and nitrogen (N₂) gases for the deposition of respective coatings. The Ar flow rate of 30 sccm was used for all the coatings deposition. Mo interlayer was deposited for 10 minutes with a sputtering power of 100 W to improve adhesion between the substrate and coatings. Optimized flow rates of CH₄ gas of 8 sccm were used for MoC coating, and 6 sccm of CH₄ and 3 sccm of N₂ gases were used for MoCN

coating deposition. In the multilayer system, similar gas flow rates were used for the deposition of MoC and MoCN layers, which consists of six bilayers of MoC and MoCN. For all coatings, a fixed sputtering power of 150 W was used for the total duration of 2 hours. The substrate temperature and target–substrate distance were kept constant at 400 °C and 70 mm, respectively. The summary of the experimental parameters used for the coating deposition are furnished in Table S1.

2.2 Coatings Characterization

X-ray photoelectron spectra (XPS) were acquired for all the coatings using a Physical Electronics Versa Probe XPS tool. This system employs a monochromated micro-focused scanning X-ray source with the Al K_{α} X-ray line (1486.6 eV), which is operated under UHV pressures ranging from 10^{-10} – 10^{-11} mbar. A dual-beam low energy electron flood gun and a low energy Ar^+ ion supply was automatically used to neutralize surface charges in the analysis region for each sample. Survey spectra were obtained with a pass energy of 112 eV and core-level spectra were generally obtained with a pass energy of 26 eV. The resultant spectra were then fitted using Gaussian– Lorentzian fit functions. Phase analysis was carried out using glancing incidence X-ray diffraction (GIXRD, Rigaku Smartlab, Japan) using Cu K_{α} radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) with 5° of incidence angle. Micro Raman analysis (Renishaw, using 532 nm laser) was carried out for the structural and chemical analysis of all the coatings. The surface properties of the coatings were analyzed using field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM, Carl Zeiss, Supra 55, Germany) and atomic force microscope (AFM, NTMDT, Russia). The elemental compositions of the as-deposited coatings were investigated using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), which included elemental mapping and spectral analysis. Nanomechanical properties were analyzed using Triboindenter (TI900, Bruker, USA). To avoid the substrate influence, the indentation depth was maintained less than 10% of coating thickness with the peak load of 9.5 mN. The

tribological properties of coatings were analyzed using linear reciprocating tribometer (DUCOM Instruments, India). The 52100 SS balls with 6 mm diameter were used as sliding counterparts with the applied load of 2N and the sliding speed of 2 cm/s. The stroke length of 5 mm and the relative humidity of ~ 40% were maintained during the tribology experiments. Coating thickness and wear depth were estimated using Dektak stylus profilometer (Bruker, USA). The detailed chemical and structural changes of all the wear tracks of the coating as well as ball scars after the tribology tests were comprehensively analyzed using XPS and Raman spectroscopy on different locations.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Chemical bonding analysis

XPS analysis was performed to probe the chemical bonding and electronic structures of as-deposited coatings. Survey spectra of all the coatings provided in Figure S1 reflected that Mo, C, and N were present as the primary elements in their respective coating. High-resolution Mo3d and C1s spectra of MoC coating, as well as Mo3d, C1s, and N1s spectra of MoCN and MOC/MoCN coatings, are shown in Figures 1a–c. For MoC coating (Figure 1a), the fitted curves of Mo3d spectra displayed well-defined three doublets, which were associated with the multiple binding energies corresponding to the Mo involved in several bonding among other elements. The Mo 3d_{5/2} and 3d_{3/2} of Mo²⁺ species observed at 228.7 and 231.9 eV, and Mo³⁺ species observed at 229.4 and 232.9 eV correspond to the covalent Mo–C bonding formation. Besides, Mo⁴⁺ and Mo⁶⁺ species were also obtained at the binding energies of ~235.1 and 236.2 eV representing the presence of MoO₃, which is well-known surface oxide formed during the exposure of coating to the atmosphere after deposition.^{23–25} C 1s spectra showed a small peak at 282.8 eV, corresponding to the Mo–C bonding due to the predominant presence of amorphous carbon chemical species C=C/C–C (284.5 eV).²⁶ The other oxide functional groups were observed at 286 eV (C–O) and 288.8 eV (C=O) because

of the presence of obvious surface oxides. The deconvoluted O1s spectra for MoC coating showed the fitted peaks ~532.1 and 533.8 eV attributed to the presence of oxygen as surface impurities.²⁶

Figure 1. High-resolution XPS spectra of (a) MoC coating (deconvoluted Mo3d, C1s, and O1s), (b) MoCN coating (deconvoluted Mo3d, C1s, and N1s), and (c) multilayer MoC/MoCN coating (deconvoluted Mo3d, C1s, and N1s). The survey spectra and core-level O 1s spectra of all the coatings are provided in supplementary data (Figure S1).

The core-level Mo 3d spectra of MoCN (Figure 1b) and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings (Figure 1c) showed that all the major six deconvoluted peaks associated with the Mo²⁺, Mo³⁺,

Mo⁴⁺ and Mo⁶⁺ species were shifted towards higher binding energies (0.2–0.4 eV) than MoC spectra with the addition of N atoms. This indicates the involvement of N atoms involving in bonding with Mo and C atoms. The peaks at 228.9 and 232.2 eV (Mo²⁺ of 3d_{5/2} and 3d_{3/2}) correspond to the C-bounded Mo and N, while the peaks with binding energies at 229.9 and 233.2 eV resembling to the N-bounded Mo, and O-bounded Mo at 235.1 and 236.2 eV in both MoCN and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings.²⁶ In the case of C 1s spectra (Figures 1b and 1c), the amorphous carbon species (C–C/C=C) peak at ~284.6 eV was slightly lower intensity than that of MoC coating. The shift of peak towards slightly higher binding energies at 286.2 (C=N/C–O) and 288.6(+0.2) eV (C–N/C=O) indicated the carbonitride formation in these coatings.^{10,23,27} The N1s spectra also further revealed multiple deconvoluted peaks attributed to graphitic–N (400.5±0.3 eV), pyrrolic–N (399.5 eV), pyridinic–N (398.2 eV), Mo–N bond (397.2 eV), Mo–C–N (394.8 eV), and oxide-N species (402.8 eV).²⁸ Surface oxides also observed in these samples, and the O 1s spectra of MoCN and MoC/MoCN samples are provided in Figure S1.

3.2 Structural analysis

Figure 2 illustrates the structural properties of coatings analyzed using GIXRD and Raman spectroscopy techniques. The GIXRD spectra of MoC coating (Figure 2a₁) showed the diffraction peaks (111), (200), (220), (311), and (222), which were attributed to the well-defined face-centered cubic (FCC) MoC phases corresponding to the standard JCPDS data (file no: 89-2868). The (111) diffraction peak obtained at 36.2° is found to be the strongest among other peaks. The estimated lattice parameter (4.278 Å) using UnitCell win software is close to the standard value (4.27 Å). The estimated strain value was also close to zero which divulges the formation of stress free MoC coating under optimized conditions. Nucleation and growth of nanocrystalline MoC grains are originated from the Mo interlayer which might promotes the possibility of attaining stress-free coating.²⁹ By introducing N, noticeable

additional peaks (at 43.5° and 63.1°) and peak broadening (increasing FWHM) of primary MoC peaks were observed in Figure 2a₂. Such diffraction patterns are closely associated to the γ -Mo₂N with FCC crystal lattice (JCPDS file no: 25–1366). Srisattayakul et al. (2017) also reported similar kind of mixed phases for MoCN coatings,⁹ in which dual phases of MoN and Mo₂C were observed at the higher N concentrations. A similar trend was also obtained for the multilayer MoC/MoCN sample, but the intensities were found to be comparatively lesser than that of the MoCN coating. The MoCN bonding formation is in good-agreement with the obtained XPS results of these specimens (Figure 1b and 1c). Since the ionic radius of C is slightly higher than that of N, the residual stress could be increased in the case of MoCN and MoC/MoCN coatings.³⁰

Figure 2. (a) X-ray diffraction patterns of (a₁) MoC, (a₂) MoCN, and (a₃) multilayer MoC/MoCN coating, and (b) Micro-Raman spectra of (b₁) MoC, (b₂) MoCN, and (b₃) multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings.

The estimated lattice parameter was found to be 4.27 Å higher than that of the standard (4.16 Å) of γ -Mo₂N affirms the presence of residual stress caused by ion bombardment. This revealed that, the MoCN and MoC/MoCN coatings possess residual stress which comprises the compressive stress caused by ion bombardment, and the tensile stress caused at the grain boundaries with the existence of excess carbon.³⁰ All the peaks were broad in nature which

indicates the nanocrystalline phases obtained with the predominant occurrences of C compounds as discussed in the XPS results. Using the Williamson-Hall method, the estimated crystallite sizes were 10, 6, and 8 nm, which corresponds to the MoC, MoCN, and MoC/MoCN coatings, respectively.

Raman spectroscopy was used to analyze the structure of carbon materials in the Raman spectrum in the range of 100–2000 cm^{-1} , as shown in Figure 2b. Two primary peaks appeared at $1385\pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and 1580 cm^{-1} correspond to the D-band and G-band in all three spectra which arises due to in plane and out of plane vibrations. The D band is originated from the out of plane sp^2 carbon vibrations resulting from the possible surface disordered nature. The G band results from the in-plane vibrations of sp^2 carbons.³¹ The proportions of D and G-bands are relatively higher for MoC coating (Figure 2b₁), and these intensities were found to decrease with the addition of N atoms (Figure 2b₂). The intensity ratio of D and G peaks (I_D/I_G) is a typical measure of defects present in the carbon-based coatings. The calculated I_D/I_G ratio was about 1.21 for MoC coatings representing the presence of sp^3/sp^2 -bonded carbons which are accumulated at the grain boundaries. The I_D/I_G ratio was increased to 2.33 for MoCN coating representing the decrease of sp^2 graphitic carbon nature by the introduction of more surface defects in the crystalline phase during the addition of N. Similarly, for multilayer MoC/MoCN coating, this ratio was about 1.77, higher than that of the MoC coating which associated with the increasing defect concentration followed by the increase of graphitic (sp^2 bonded) carbons.^{17,32} Generally, Raman spectra are inactive for stoichiometric compounds due to the center of inversion (C_i) symmetry, and hence no major peaks were observed for the Mo-based cubic features of all the coatings as observed from GIXRD results. However, the observed weak bands at 886 cm^{-1} and 954 cm^{-1} correspond to the possible surface defects at the grain boundaries with the N addition in MoCN and MoC/MoCN coatings.

3.3 Surface and cross-sectional analysis

The 2D AFM topographies and FESEM morphologies revealed that the existence of uniformly distributed particles and defect/crack-free surfaces were obtained for all the coatings (Figure 3). The measured particle sizes were in the range of ~425 nm, 470 nm, and 401 nm corresponding to the MoC, MoCN, and MoC/MoCN multilayer, respectively. Also, these surfaces were very smooth, with a mean roughness of ~ 4.8 nm, 3.5 nm and 4.5 nm. Particle size determination and line profile analysis for roughness estimation of these coatings are presented in the supporting data (Figure S2). The particles followed a similar trend but with higher values compared to the estimated crystallite sizes from the GIXRD results. This revealed that the coalescence of smaller crystallites formed led to larger particles in all the coatings. The higher surface to volume ratio and higher surface energy of smaller crystallites favour to attach the crystallites together and get embedded in the amorphous carbon matrix.

The cross-sectional morphologies (Figure 3d–f) also illustrated that many small channels like columnar growth originated from the Mo interlayer and ended up with spherical topped bigger particles. The continuous columnar structure of the MoC coating was discovered, but the columnar structure was slightly deteriorated when N atoms were introduced into the MoC lattice during MoCN deposition. This could be due to the formation of MoC and MoN lattice structure in MoCN coating, as observed from the GIXRD result. Besides, clear multilayer interfaces are obviously seen, and the sharp interfaces between MoC and MoCN alternate layers are shown in Figure 3f as well as Figure S3. Herein, the columnar structure of the underlayer (MoC or MoCN) was terminated at the interfaces and new columnar growth of overlayer was initiated, and vice versa during the deposition of alternate layers. The coating thickness of 3.3 μm , 3.2 μm , and 3.5 μm was observed for MoC, MoCN and MoC/MoCN coatings, respectively. Elemental mapping and compositional analysis of the as-deposited coatings analyzed on the cross-sectional morphologies are shown in Figure S4. The relative

atomic contents of the coatings measured by EDX are shown in Table 1. The content of Mo (30–33 at.%) is relatively similar because of the same sputtering power, while highest content of C (66.13 at.%) observed in MoC coating. With the addition of N, the C content of MoCN and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings decreased slightly to 56.96, and 60.95 at.%, respectively.

Figure 3. AFM surface topographies and FESEM morphologies of (a) & (d) MoC, (b) & (e) MoCN, and (c) & (f) multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings. (In Figure (a) – (c), G and GB representing the grain and grain boundaries, respectively).

Table 1. Chemical composition of as-deposited MoC, MoCN, and MoC/MoCN coatings.

Sample	Elements (Atomic %)		
	Mo	C	N
MoC	33.87	66.13	--
MoCN	29.94	56.96	13.10
MoC/MoCN	30.63	60.95	8.42

3.4 Nanomechanical and Tribological Properties

3.4.1 Hardness (H), elastic modulus (E), and resistance to plastic deformation (H^3/E^2)

The estimated nanomechanical properties of MoC, MoCN, and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings, as well as uncoated 316L SS substrates, are furnished in Table 2. The load-displacement curves used to estimate the nanomechanical properties are presented in Figure S5. The average indentation depths of ~198, 212, 183, and 320 nm were obtained for the MoC, MoCN, MoC/MoCN coatings and 316L SS substrates, respectively. The estimated elastic recovery was also found to be higher ~48% for multilayer MoC/MoCN coating, and this elastic nature was lower of about 42% for MoC, and the least values (~36%) were observed for the MoCN coating as well as bare 316L SS substrates (~38%). The mean hardness and modulus were found to be 18 ± 2 GPa and 226.5 ± 20 GPa for MoC coating, whereas these values decreased with the addition of N and were found to be 16.8 ± 2.5 GPa and 208.4 ± 25 GPa respectively. In the case of multilayer coating, these properties increased to the maximum value, 21.5 ± 2 GPa and 236.2 ± 25 GPa compared to other samples. The hardness and modulus are much lower for bare substrates of 3.7 ± 0.3 GPa and 160.6 ± 10 GPa, respectively. The improved mechanical properties could be due to the change in grain structure as well as multilayer architecture, and hence, the plastic deformation impedes at the crystalline grain boundaries along with multilayer interfaces. The H^3/E^2 also followed a similar trend for all the respective coatings. It has been reported that the grain rotation might be the possible mechanism of plastic deformation in nanocrystalline coatings with the grain sizes >10 nm.³³ The addition of N into the MoC coating leads to higher possible grain boundary defects resulting in lower nanomechanical properties in MoCN coating. On the other hand, the enriched sp^2 carbons as seen in XPS and Raman studies, could be the possible reason for the plastic behavior of coatings with lower elastic recovery.

Table 2. Nanomechanical properties (H, E and H^3/E^2) of MoC, MoCN, and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings as well as uncoated 316L SS substrates.

Sample	Hardness, H (GPa)	Elastic Modulus, E (GPa)	H^3/E^2 (GPa)	Elastic Recovery (%)
MoC	18 ± 2	226.5 ± 20	0.114 ± 0.006	42
MoCN	16.8 ± 2.5	208.4 ± 25	0.109 ± 0.008	36
MoC/MoCN	21.5 ± 2	236.2 ± 25	0.178 ± 0.006	48
316L SS (Bare)	3.7 ± 0.3	160.6 ± 10	0.002	38

3.4.2 Friction and wear behavior of coatings

The tribological properties of the coatings were evaluated under ambient conditions using the 52100 SS balls as sliding counterbodies. The friction curves and their corresponding wear depth profiles are provided in Figures 4a and b. All the friction curves are smooth and highly stable throughout the experiments. The tests were repeated three times to assess the standard deviation of friction coefficient (CoF) and wear rate under similar tribological conditions, and the results are shown in Figure 4a–c. The estimated hertzian contact pressure was found to be 0.846, 0.824 and 0.857 GPa for the MoC, MoCN, and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings, respectively. The average CoF obtained was 0.32 ± 0.05 for MoC, 0.46 ± 0.08 for MoCN, and 0.3 ± 0.08 for MoC/MoCN coatings under similar conditions. The lower wear depth and smooth wear profile were observed for multilayer MoC/MoCN and MoC coatings as seen in Figure 4b. The wear resistance (Figure 4c) was found to be higher for the MoC/MoCN multilayer coating with the wear rate of $8.7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ followed by MoC coating ($3.9 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$). In the case of MoCN coating, a higher wear depth (~2150 nm) with the irregular curve was obtained revealing the lower wear resistance of $\sim 7.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ and these possible wear scars are developed due to the trapping of third body wear particles at the

interacting interfaces. These particles are hard enough to produce deep scratches on the coating surface representing abrasive nature because of the reduced mechanical properties.³⁴ The friction (0.64 ± 0.08) and wear rate ($9.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$) were found to be significantly higher for the bare 316L SS substrates.

Figure 4. (a) Friction coefficient (Inset: average friction coefficient with standard deviation), and (b) Wear profile analysis of (i) MoC, (ii) MoCN, (iii) multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings and (iv) uncoated 316L SS substrates tested under ambient atmospheric conditions, and (c) the estimated wear rate (k) of each sample after the tribology test. [Coating thickness more than 3 microns. Tribology Parameters: Ball: SS (6 mm Dia.); Load: 2N; Stroke: 5 mm; Sliding Speed: 3 cm/s; Temp: RT; Sliding Distance: 210 m; RH: 40%].

3.5 Tribochemical analysis

3.5.1 Chemical bonding analysis on the wear tracks of MoC, MoCN and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings using XPS

Tribochemistry analysis on the wear tracks of coatings post tribology tests was analyzed using XPS. Three different locations (i.e., location 1 – middle of the wear track, location 2 – deformed area, and location 3 – edge) of wear tracks were examined to observe the change in chemical state for all the coatings. Figure 5(a–e) shows the core-level spectra of Mo3d, C1s, O1s, Fe2p components, and survey spectra of the wear track of MoC coating.

Figure 5. X-ray photoelectron analysis on the wear track at different locations of MoC coating, high-resolution spectra of the elements (a) Mo3d, (b) C1s, (c) O1s, (d) Fe2p and (e) survey spectra. [(a₁–e₁) location 1 – middle of the wear track, (a₂–e₂) location 2 – deformed area, and (a₃–e₃) location 3 – edge].

Survey spectra (Figure 5(e)) disclosed that the primary elements (Mo, and C) from the coating, as well as reactive O from the atmosphere and mild transfer of the element Fe from the sliding counterbody were also observed in the MoC wear track. The deconvoluted Mo3d spectra on all three regimes (Figure 5a) show the Mo²⁺ and Mo³⁺ species of Mo 3d_{5/2} of Mo 3d_{3/2} fitted curves which are almost similar to the MoC surface (Figure 1a). However, the Mo⁴⁺ and Mo⁶⁺ species were noticeably increased, representing the formation of molybdenum oxides (such as MoO₃ and MoO₂) on the wear surface. The obvious chemical

reactions between Mo and atmospheric oxygen during continuous sliding interactions are obviously due to the higher contact stress and flash temperature in localized area which activated the coated surface to oxidize by means of mechanochemical process.³⁵ More specifically, these species are dominated at the edge of the wear tracks which is denoted with higher intensity. This is also further evidenced as the C–O/C=O (~288.8 eV) bonding increased as seen in the C1s spectra at location 3 (Figure 5(b₃)).^{10,36} The oxidized carbons were found to be rich at the edge of the wear track, while the graphitic sp² bonded carbons (284.7 eV) were enriched inside the wear track because of the lower exposure to atmospheric oxygen as seen in C1s spectra (locations 1 and 2). More interestingly, the peak at 285.3±0.1 eV is attributed to the signature of sp³ bonded carbons, which signifies the hard diamond-like features also obtained during the tribo-interactions. Such transition of carbon is possible due to the reaction with atmospheric H with free carbons and C–C bonding due to higher contact stress/and high flash temperature which promotes the endothermic phase transformation.³⁷ Figure 5d represents minor fractions of Fe present on the edge of the wear track, but inside the ball materials are not attached to the MoC surface. The peaks centered at 711.7 and 725.6 eV corresponds to the Fe₂O₃ bondings.³⁸ The metal oxides of MoO₃ and small fraction of Fe₂O₃ are also evidenced from the binding energies of 528.5 (±0.1), 533.9 (±0.1), and 535 (±0.3) eV of O1s spectra (Figure 5(c)).

Figure 6. X-ray photoelectron analysis on the wear track at different locations of MoCN coating, high-resolution spectra of the elements (a) Mo3d, (b) C1s, (c) N1s, (d) O1s, (e) Fe2p and (f) survey spectra. [(a₁-f₁) location 1 – middle of the wear track, (a₂-f₂) location 2 – deformed area inside the wear track, and (a₃-f₃) location 3 – edge of the track].

Figure 6 displays the XPS spectra on the wear track of MoCN coating. Core-level Mo3d spectrum suggested that the Mo3d_{5/2} peaks of Mo²⁺ and Mo³⁺ species are only present at the edge of the wear track (location 3), whereas these Mo-C bonding disappears inside the wear track as seen in Figure 6a. On the other hand, Mo3d_{3/2} of Mo²⁺ (228.7 eV) and Mo³⁺ (232 eV) species attributed to the substoichiometric bonding between Mo and C elements, which shifted to the higher binding energy compared to that of the coating surface. The enhancement of Mo⁴⁺ (235.3 eV) and Mo⁶⁺ (236.2 eV) species ensured the MoO₃ formation which could be due to the chemical interaction of O with Mo. Figure 6b, the fitted curves

based on the core-level C1s spectra majorly exhibit sp^2 carbons (C=C) at 284.6 ± 0.1 eV followed by sp^3 carbons (C-H/C-C) at 285.3 ± 0.2 eV and oxide species (O=C-O) at 288.7 ± 0.1 eV.^{36,37} N1s spectra (Figure 6c) demonstrate that the pyrrolic-N (~ 399.3 eV) was more predominant than other species compared to the MoCN surface caused by the hydrogen-terminated nitrogen with five-membered rings during tribological interactions.³⁷ Trace amount of graphitic N (402.8 eV) and Mo-C-N (395 eV) could be observed in the wear track and wear debris, respectively. Fe and O (Figure 6d and e) were present in all three locations which could be anticipated from the thin tribolayer formation on the wear track that consists of metal oxides (Fe_2O_3 and MoO_3). The periodic formation and removal of thin oxidized tribolayer consisting of Mo and Fe-based oxides could have taken place on this sample. Periodic oxidation also has an influence on the tribological properties of MoCN coating, due to which the surface was prone to abrasive wear and resulted lower wear resistance.^{39,40}

Figure 7 illustrates the XPS spectra of elements composing on the wear track of multilayer MoC/MoCN coating. As seen in the wear profile, the wear resistance of this coating was superior as the core-level spectra is found to be almost similar to the surface of this coating (Figure 1c). Mild influence of atmospheric oxygen was also observed from the peak shift towards higher binding energies (~ 0.1 eV) of core-level Mo 3d spectra (Figure 7a). It can be seen that the intensity for MoO_3 (236.2 ± 0.2 eV) was increased considerably which suggests the increase of Mo^{6+} species of $3d_{5/2}$ than that of the coating surface. The fraction of sp^2 bonded carbons (C=C) slightly decreased while the pyrrolic-N ($\sim 399.5\pm 0.3$ eV) and Mo-C-N (~ 395.3 eV) increased in the wear track.^{38,41} The diamond like sp^3 features also increased at 285.3 ± 0.2 eV (Figure 7b) in all the locations of this sample which signifies a thick as well as hard tribolayer which was formed on the wear track. The O1s spectra (Figure 7d) showed the occurrence of MoO_2 and MoO_3 phases, and the presence of a minor amount of Fe_2O_3

species was also observed in the wear track. From the observation of the XPS analysis, it can be presumed that (i) the presence of the stable sp^2 and sp^3 hybridized carbons, and (ii) pyrrolic-N plays the two key governing roles for friction and wear behavior of multilayer MoC/MoCN coating. Other possible factors might be the mild influence of tribo oxides, humidity, improved mechanical properties, dense microstructure, and multilayer architecture.

Figure 7. X-ray photoelectron analysis on the wear track at different locations of multilayer MoC/MoCN coating, high-resolution spectra of the elements (a) Mo3d, (b) C1s, (c) N1s, (d) O1s, (e) Fe2p and (f) survey spectra. [(a₁–f₁) location 1 – middle of the wear track, (a₂–f₂) location 2 – deformed area inside the wear track, and (a₃–f₃) location 3 – edge of the track].

3.5.2 Tribochemical analysis of MoC, MoCN and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings and ball counterbodies using Raman spectroscopy

Tribochemical products were characterized using Raman spectroscopy to examine the structural changes of the coatings post tribology tests. Similar to XPS analyses, three different locations were examined to complete the analysis of the wear tracks, and the resultant spectra are shown in Figure 8. The optical images represent the corresponding Raman spectra recorded spots, namely, plain area (a_1 – c_1), wear debris (a_2 – c_2), and the edge of the wear tracks (a_3 – c_3) (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Raman spectra on the wear track of (a) MoC, (b) MoCN, (c) MoC/MoCN coatings. Optical micrographs of the wear track indicating three different locations (a_1 – a_3 in MoC, b_1 – b_3 in MoCN, and c_1 – c_3 in MoC/MoCN coatings) where the Raman spectra were recorded.

The optical micrographs clearly show that wear tracks are free from the presence of wear particles, third bodies, and tribolayer, which were derived outside the sliding interface as well as attached to the ball counter surface. Such interesting behavior is only obtained for molybdenum-based coatings, and these results are also well-reported in the previous reports.^{14,19} Very stable and uniform wear morphology was obtained for MoC coating. Deep scratches were observed on the MoCN coating because of its lower resistance to plastic deformation and abrasive wear nature. Also, several severe local fatigue failures are also

observed in this sample. Minor patches of fatigue failure can be seen in the multilayer of MoC/MoCN coatings. Local failure in these coatings occurs because of the possible surface defects and deformed grain boundaries with the addition of N. Moreover, the higher contact stress during the continuous sliding process leads to originate the minor cracks followed by fracture of these coatings. It can be seen that the spot 1(a₁-c₁) shows similar spectral results of the coatings' surface (Figure 2b), revealing no residues of wear debris and/or tribolayer attached on the wear interfaces. In the case of spots 2(a₂-c₂) and 3(a₃-c₃), the observed lower region (200–500 cm⁻¹), and mid-region (700–1000 cm⁻¹) peaks are corresponding to the metal oxides, while the higher region (1200–1800 cm⁻¹) peaks correspond to the carbon content (D and G bands). Raman shifts are attributed to the different phase formation in all three coatings. These peaks correspond to the different bands of tribochemical products such as Mo=O bending vibrations in the lower region bands at 188 – 350 cm⁻¹, Mo–O–Mo symmetry stretching (519 cm⁻¹), Mo–O–Mo asymmetry stretching (586 cm⁻¹), and Mo–O–Mo deformation stretching (775±3 cm⁻¹).¹⁴ Besides, the obtained strong band at 922 cm⁻¹ (Mo=O stretching) is attributed to the significant presence of molybdenum oxide (MoO₃), especially at the locations 2(a₂-c₂) and 3(a₃-c₃) of all three samples.⁴² Similar to the XPS findings, the tribo-induced transformation of sp² to sp³ nature of carbons skeleton was observed which results the shift of the D band to the lower wavenumber (~1355 cm⁻¹) due to the alteration in bond strain. All these complex tribochemical products were transferred outside the wear track and also attached to the sliding ball counterface.

To investigate tribochemical reactions further, the ball scar also was examined for phase analysis using Raman spectroscopy, and the resultant spectra recorded on three different regions are shown in Figure 9(a–c). The corresponding optical images of these spectral spots are illustrated in Figure S6. It can be seen that D (1357±19 cm⁻¹) and G (1590±5 cm⁻¹) bands of carbons were majorly present in all the locations, along with minor oxide peaks.

Remarkably, these carbons were enriched inside the ball scar (a₂-c₂) which also evidenced from the optical microscope images consist of the strong tribolayer (dark patches) with good adhesion. The out diffused carbons from the respective coatings were deposited on the ball surface as graphite-like carbon tribolayer is providing sufficient lubrication and wear resistance. The tribology mechanism can be explained by the initial wear that takes place on both the sliding surface. Later on, the free carbons from the respective coatings are transferred to the ball surface and form the active tribolayer. The basal planes in the graphitic tribolayer are connected through weak Van der Waals force, while the inter-planar carbons are bonded through sp² covalent bonds. This interplanar sp² carbons generally exhibit low shear resistance exhibiting low friction and wear.^{43,44} XPS results also revealed the formation of various carbon bonds inside the wear track alters the mechanical properties resulting in the improved tribological properties of MoC and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings. In addition, different chemical species of carbons (as identified from the XPS results) in the tribolayer (C–C/C=C, C–H, C–O–N, and C–O bonds) under humid atmosphere could also have a mild influence on the tribo-mechanical properties.⁴⁵ On the other hand, the role of oxides was not observed for the MoC coatings (Figure 9(a₁-a₃)), while the noticeable oxides (lower bands 196–922 cm⁻¹) were seen for MoCN coating. In the case of MoC/MoCN multilayer coating, the oxides predominately seen outside the wear track (c₃) reveals the oxidized wear debris from coating and ball materials deposited with enriched MoO₃ and Fe₂O₃ phases (148–985 cm⁻¹). Overall, it is interesting to notice that the concentration of tribolayer on ball surface was higher than that of the coating wear track, as evidenced from the Raman intensities and optical micrographs. The previous reports¹⁴ also demonstrated a similar transfer layer especially from Mo based coatings; and it still requires further investigation to explain the unusual reaction mechanism.

Figure 9. Raman spectra on the 52100 SS ball sliding surface against the (a) MoC, (b) MoCN, and (c) multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings. Three different regions were analyzed (a₁–c₁) interface region, (a₂–c₂) inside wear scar, and (a₃–c₃) outside wear scar as illustrated in Figure S6. At least six different spots [S1–S6] of each region were analyzed to cover the overall surface.

3.6 Tribological mechanism of MoC, MoCN and MoC/MoCN coatings

The above findings reveal that the friction and wear mechanisms of different Mo based coatings are originated from the coating characteristics; and later, the nature of tribolayer governing the tribological properties. Besides, the humid atmosphere also has a favorable role in the enhanced tribological performance due to the chemisorption of the water molecule.^{45,46} The formation of carbon dangling σ -bonds of carbon network under humid conditions would

improve the stability of the transferred tribolayer on MoC and MoC/MoCN coatings.⁴⁵ Although the friction coefficient is almost similar for all the coatings, wear resistance of multilayer MoC/MoCN, and MoC coatings are superior than that of MoCN coating, as shown in Figure 4b. During initial sliding cycles, such enhanced wear resistance of these coatings can be directly related to the improved mechanical and refined grain structure that effectively obstructs the crack initiation and propagation. But the columnar microstructure and lower hardness deliver poor resistance against wear in MoCN coatings. Such rapid wear behavior is clearly indicated by the sharp increase of wear depth as seen in the wear profile (Figure 4b). After some sliding cycles, the detached wear debris, the out diffused excess carbons, and their reactive products become the leading influencing factors in all the coatings. Figure 10(a–c) illustrates the different possible tribochemical reactions and tribolayer formations in MoC, MoCN, and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings.

Figure 10. Schematic illustrations of tribology mechanisms in 52100 SS balls sliding against (a) MoC, (b) MoCN, and (c) multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings. [P-N and G-N refers to the pyrrolic-N and graphitic-N, respectively].

From the XPS, Raman spectra, and optical micrograph results, it is evidenced that the tribolayer and chemical species are present in both the sliding surfaces. Depending on the nature of chemical species, constituents, and tribolayer stability, the wear resistance is varied among the coatings. The sp^2 (graphite-like) and sp^3 (diamond-like) bonded carbons, and minimum amount of metal oxides were the tribolayer constituent on all the interacting surfaces as obtained from the C1s XPS spectra and the distinct D and G bands from Raman analysis. Due to the increase of sp^3 carbon characteristics in the tribolayer and less influence of oxides in the sliding interface (Figure 10a), the MoC coating provides low wear rate, while the sp^2 carbon on both surfaces provides sufficient lubricity. As illustrated in Figure 10c, the presence of predominant concentration of graphitic like sp^2 carbons on the ball surface, sp^3 carbons, graphitic-N on both interacting surfaces, and the improved hardness due to multilayer architecture; the strain hardening takes place on the wear track resulting in superior wear resistance for multilayer MoC/MoCN coating. Although the tribolayer consists of noticeable sp^2 and sp^3 carbons and graphitic-N (as shown in Figure 10b), the lower mechanical properties of MoCN coating experience frequent fatigue failure and causes more wear particles. On the other hand, the presence of N in MoCN coating, it could reduce the chemical reactions between wear debris and the atmosphere owing to its inert nature.⁴⁵ Here the N terminates the C-H bonds frequently and resulting thin tribolayer, as seen in the optical micrographs (Figure S6), and also evident from the XPS results (Figure 6). The nanoindentation results (Figure 4a) also demonstrated poor resistance to the plastic deformation behavior of the coating.

4.0 Conclusions

Newly developed carbon rich MoC, MoCN, and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings were studied to explore their tribological properties under ambient conditions. Chemical bonding

results revealed that the covalent bonding (i.e., Mo–C, Mo–C–N) was observed between the primary elements along with the excess carbon features (i.e., C=C, C–N). Structural results indicate the cubic structure of MoC, and MoCN phases present in the respective coatings. Tribological properties demonstrate that the MoC and multilayer MoC/MoCN coatings show low friction and enhanced wear resistant nature, while MoCN coating exhibits poor tribomechanical properties. Extremely low wear rate of MoC ($3.9 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$) and multilayer MoC/MoCN ($8.7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$) coatings, while the poor wear resistance ($7.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$) were obtained for MoCN coating. Initially, the structural and mechanical properties of the respective coatings have shown profound influence on the tribological properties. Nevertheless, the tribochemical analysis by XPS and Raman spectroscopy revealed the formation and nature of tribofilms play a huge role on the wear behavior of these coatings rather less influence of tribo-oxides. The predominant graphitic carbons (sp^2) that exist in the tribofilms act as a dissipating medium of contact stress which prevents further wear of interacting surfaces. Tribo-induced formations of sp^3 bonded carbons (diamond-like) inside the wear track also enhance the hardness of tribofilms. The co-existence of sp^2 and sp^3 carbon in MoC coating, along with noticeable pyrrolic–N in multilayer MoC/MoCN coating prevails superior tribological performances. In the case of MoCN coating, N restricts the C–H bond formation confining the strong tribofilms formation, and hence poor wear resistance. Moreover, the lower hardness of this sample leads to abrasive wear and subsequent exposure of fresh surfaces result in the possibility of weaker tribofilms on MoCN coating. Refined grain structure, multilayer architecture, enhanced mechanical properties, and sp^3 carbons rich tribofilms with other carbon species are also played a favourable role on the superior wear resistance nature of multilayer coating.

Supporting Information

The supporting information includes the experimental parameters used for the coating deposition, XPS survey spectra, particle size determination from AFM, EDX elemental mapping, load-displacement curves, and Raman mapping images for better understanding on the deposition and characterization of carbon-rich Mo-based coatings for tribological applications.

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